

Airborne Photonics, A Technology Whose Time Has Come

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ABSTRACT

The past twenty years has seen the rapid introduction of fiber optic hardware into commercial telecommunications networks because of the cost and performance advantages that the technology provides. The aerospace industry has also been engaged in research and development to apply the technology to military and commercial aircraft. The specific applications of photonic technology to aircraft can be organized into the following categories:

- point-to-point fiber optic data transmission to replace copper wiring
- high speed networks and computer interconnects
- flight and engine controls generally known as "fly-by-light"
- smart skins and smart structures

The projected advantages of fiber optic systems are: very high bandwidth (unachievable with wire), EMI/EMP immunity (without the need for additional shielding), weight/volume /cost savings over wire for equivalent high bandwidth applications and elimination of spark induced fire hazards.

This paper reviews present applications of fiber optics to aircraft as well as recent significant photonic component and systems advances in both the commercial and military sector which will provide new capabilities which cannot be achieved with wire. Novel components which will be described include improved fibers, cables, connectors, couplers, lasers, amplifiers, modulators, and sensors. Novel broadband network concepts which will be described use multiple fiber channel redundancy to provide built-in fault prediction, isolation, and circumvention without the weight, volume, cost, or performance penalties of alternative wire or fiber approaches. Implementation of systems of this type in both avionics and control systems can provide in-flight diagnostics and real time reconfiguration of the cable plant with elimination or minimization of data loss during reconfiguration. The status of optical backplane development and acceptance of commercial standards for avionics applications will also be discussed. If the aircraft community expends the resources to exploit these recent advances now, photonic systems will become the technology of choice in our production aircraft before the turn of the century.

BACKGROUND

The avionics community has been predicting the widespread use of fiber optics in aircraft for the past twenty years because of the clear advantages that the technology offers. Even with the

projected benefits, the application of fiber optics technology to aircraft has been impeded by technical, economic and/or perceived risk factors. Manufacturers are comfortable with copper cables, connectors and sensors even though this proven technology poses reliability and maintenance problems and imposes a weight penalty on aircraft. Fiber optic hardware is much more expensive than the electrical counterparts on a piece-part comparison and the reliability of the components is unproven especially in avionic environments. Fiber optic connectors are perceived as difficult to install, maintain, and repair. Test or repair equipment is costly and additional training is required. There is fear that a fiber or component failure can bring down the entire network and most commercial component standards are inadequate for aircraft. These risk items drive most program managers from selecting the rapidly advancing fiber optics technology for a new platform. A fiber optic system must provide clear life cycle cost advantages and performance benefits which greatly exceed those of a comparable wire system if the technology is to be selected as an integral part of the avionic system during the development phase of an acquisition program. I will briefly review the status of fiber optics applications in aerospace platforms.

WHAT FIBER HARDWARE IS IN PRODUCTION?

The only fiber optic hardware which is in production at this time consists of a limited number of point-to-point links which transfer data between avionics "black boxes". These links use short wavelength LEDs, multimode fiber cables, silicon PIN photodiodes and fiber optic connectors which were based on past electrical connector design (e.g. SMA or MIL-STD 38999). These links in the F/A-18, AV-8B, and the blackhawk helicopter have performed reasonably well at data rates from 10KBPS-100MBPS considering the severe avionics environment in which they have operated. The relatively low data rates and low volume production rates have kept cost high for the fiber optic hardware to date. Because of this increased cost, these links are used only where a severe EMI/EMP problem exists.

NETWORKS IN MILITARY AND COMMERCIAL AIRCRAFT

Military and commercial aircraft have been using a networked architecture for the past twenty years. The dominant network protocol for military aircraft, a command response control approach, was designed for real-time applications (i.e. MIL-STD-1553) and uses twisted shielded pair (TSP) copper wire as the transmission media.

The commercial aircraft has also adopted networked architectures for avionics applications. Commercial aviation has adopted an electrical bus standard through the airlines electronic engineering committee (AEEC). These architecture standards are drafted and supported through Aeronautical Radio Inc (ARINC) just as MIL-STD-1553 has been supported through the Society of Automotive Engineers (SAE) Aeronautical Systems Division (ASD). The benefits of networked architectures are well recognized throughout the commercial avionics industry.

The Tactical Information Exchange System (TIES) which was developed by the Naval Air Development Center was the first attempt to introduce a broadband network concept which fully integrated digital and analog information on a single network in the mid-seventies. The concept used CATV transmission technology, with digital modulation techniques, to provide multichannel capability to systems over a coaxial transmission media. The system was never adopted for production although the technology was a fore-runner of the broadband fiber optic technology being proposed for today's military and commercial aircraft.

FIBER NETWORKS HAVE FINALLY ARRIVED

To maintain the standard avionics interface compatibility with existing avionics architectures, the first attempt to introduce fiber optic networks in military aircraft used a fiber optic implementation of the command response protocol known as MIL-STD-1773. The data rate was maintained at the same 1 Mbit per second (although higher speed versions have been proposed and implemented on other platforms). Since this network provides the equivalent performance (and added EMI/EMP immunity) of the TSP version, at a higher cost, it has not been adopted for any U.S. aircraft at this time. A NASA spacecraft is currently deployed using the MIL-STD-1773 network with excellent results in a hostile environment. The European Fighter Aircraft (EFA) Program has also developed a higher data rate version of the standard designated STANAG 3910 but the fiber optic version was not selected for the first prototype aircraft.

The introduction of integrated avionics during the development of new military aircraft (A-12, F-22, and the RAH-66) presented an opportunity to introduce a new avionics architecture into aircraft incorporating a high speed fiber optic network. These advanced platforms departed from the "black box" approach to aircraft integration and based their packaging on the use of standard modules and integrated racks. The basic functional building block became the electronic module rather than the avionics black box. A high speed fiber optic data bus replaced MIL-STD-1553 as the main avionics bus used to interconnect the integrated racks and other sub-systems. This bus uses a token passing protocol based on SAE standard AS4074.1 and a linear star-coupled topology. The interconnections between individual modules within the integrated rack utilizes an electrical multilayer board backplane transmission media. This multilayer electrical backplane protocol standard is a parallel bus standard developed by the IEEE known as the PI bus.

The hardware for the first military fiber optic aircraft network is currently being developed and qualified. The cable uses a 100/140 micrometer multimode graded index fiber with hermetic coating and a polyimide coating. The connectors use butt joint fiber optic termini with a modified MIL-STD-38999 backshell. As this first generation hardware is being developed, a commonality working group has been formed to achieve commonality of fiber optic hardware on the F-22, RAH-66 and future Navy aircraft

FIBER IN COMMERCIAL AIRCRAFT

Fiber optic technology is now also emerging into commercial aircraft. There have been extensive development efforts to date for commercial aircraft but the systems are not yet in production. The Boeing 777 aircraft will be the first commercial aircraft to implement a fiber optic network. It will implement a protocol and counter-rotating ring topology based on the ANSI Fiber Distributed Data Interface (FDDI) standard. This network known as PLANENET which uses the commercially developed protocol and microcircuit implementation however will not use the commercially prescribed FDDI standard fiber optic hardware but will use hardware which has been specifically designed to meet the aerospace environmental requirements. The hardware implementation is similar to that used in military platforms. The AEEC of ARINC is finalizing Specification 636 for an Onboard Local Area Network.

WHAT HAS DELAYED THE TECHNOLOGY?

Why hasn't fiber technology, which has such potentially high pay-off because of the obvious advantages, been implemented sooner in military and commercial aircraft? The answer is not a simple one since a combination of technological, economic, and "cultural" factors are involved. Let me attempt to identify some of the issues.

During the 1970's when the military first attempted to introduce fiber optics into aircraft, the commercial telecommunications industry was preoccupied with the applications of the technology to long haul point-to-point communications for the phone companies. The technical solutions for long distance transmission were totally incompatible with the hardware required for aircraft networks. Long wavelength lasers, single mode fibers, and avalanche photodiodes were the components of choice in order to meet the long distance transmission requirements. These requirements called for extremely long distances between repeaters, the lowest possible signal attenuation and minimal pulse dispersion with the highest possible data transmission rate. The environment in which the telecommunication lines were installed is rather benign when contrasted with aircraft platforms. Even the severe undersea transcontinental environment, though more of a challenge to the technology than that of terrestrial lines, is very stable and predictable when contrasted with aerospace requirements. This long line telecommunication market has dominated component development during the seventies and eighties. The single mode hardware of the telecommunications industry simply could not operate over the aircraft environment and was not designed for network applications.

The aircraft network applications during this period required components which could operate over extremes of temperature, vibration and shock. The data rates were low but the aircraft assembly and installation techniques dictated the need for a large number of in-line connectors. Little or no advances were emerging from the laboratories at this time on advanced network protocols and topologies even though university, government and industry research and development were being heavily supported. "Ethernet", a carrier sense detect multiple access (CSDMA) protocol pioneered by the Xerox Palo Alto research center emerged as a dominant low data rate network standard for interconnecting computer peripherals. Unfortunately, this protocol was entirely incompatible with aircraft real-time requirements. The bottom line is that there was no commercial interest or market for fiber optic networks during this period on which the military could resort for hardware, standards or talent. Most of the commercial telecommunications network research was centered on wide area network (WAN) protocol development and used the transport layer provided by the phone company long lines. The aircraft community was indeed ahead of its time in implementing local area networks into systems but there was minimal fiber optic hardware available in the commercial marketplace to support this application.

Because ethernet was considered more than adequate for commercial applications, fiber optics was not impacting the commercial networking market. The lasers and single mode components of the telecommunications market could not operate reliably over the aircraft environment. Even if the components could be screened to operate over aerospace environments, the cost of the components was prohibitive for low data rate network applications where a large number of terminals were required. The other key components for network applications, couplers and switches, received very little commercial development support during this period due to lack of a commercial market.

In addition to the component problems, another issue which is often overlooked when studying the history of applications of fiber optic in aerospace platforms is the retro-fit problem. In order to communicate on a network, every box or system must contain a network interface card with fiber optic transmitters and receivers. Although a network standard was in use (MIL-STD 1553), agreement on a modulation format for the optical interface needed to be reached since the bi-polar signal approach of 1553 is incompatible with optical transmission. This was eventually done through the SAE and adopted in MIL-STD 1773. The cost of retrofitting every box in an avionics system with an optical interface and re-qualifying the hardware was prohibitive to most program managers. The lack of a standard backplane and open systems hardware approach also made retro-fit a very costly proposition. The lack of accepted test equipment and repair procedures for the fiber optic cable plant hardware also posed risk considered unacceptable to most program managers.

The fiber optic hardware which is now being applied to aerospace networks is the result of funded component developments by the government and aerospace companies.

The use of short wavelength multimode hardware consisting of 850 nm LEDs and silicon PIN photodiodes provides a cost effective solution and provided performance adequate to meet performance over the aerospace environment. Long wavelength multimode sources and detectors are now also being qualified. Most fiber optic connectors are based on modifications to existing electrical connectors to achieve commonality with existing cabling approaches. The fiber optic hardware has performed reliably but the low volume of use has not produced the lower cost hardware once envisioned.

THE NEW COMMERCIAL EMPHASIS IN FIBER OPTIC NETWORKING :

A: THE COMPUTER INDUSTRY

The proliferation of personal computers has given birth to a tremendous resurgence of interest in local area networks that did not exist in the nineteen seventies. Unfortunately, the emphasis on long distance communications and wide area networking during the late seventies and eighties pre-empted development of a family of low cost fiber components optimized for high speed networking applications by our fledgling electro-optic component industry. During the eighties however, the computer industry adopted a local area network protocol standard designated as the Fiber Distributed Data Interface (FDDI) based on a token passing protocol operating at 100 Mbit per second which was considered to be extremely high for LANs at the time of proposal. The dominance of the fiber optic telecommunications marketplace strongly influenced the selection of the 1.3 micrometer wavelength as the optical wavelength of choice for this LAN standard even though the requirements did not dictate this selection based on data rate or distance requirements. The cost penalty associated with the selection of this 1.3 micrometer operating wavelength for the industry FDDI 100 MB/sec local area network standard has delayed the use of fiber optics as the preferred media for networks. An 850 nanometer solution would have permitted implementation with much lower cost GaAs LEDs and silicon PIN photodiodes. This could have dramatically boosted the market for such devices which were already adopted by the military to provide high volume and reduce costs.

Today the commercial industry is reverting back to Twisted Shielded Pair (TSP) or Unshielded Twisted Pair (UTP) copper to implement the FDDI protocol to reduce costs and is adopting new modulation standards to accommodate these lower cost media. One wonders if this is really the market place speaking or if this is the final gasp of the copper wire industry trying to block the inevitable entry of glass as the dominant transmission media of the next century.

As the high volume of fiber optic hardware use is delayed by this series of events, the need for higher bandwidth networks is being driven by multimedia applications, the integration of audio, video and data over the same network. A dramatic reduction in the cost of multimode components (i.e. LED based transmitters and receivers) is required for the existing FDDI standard or else the use of copper will prevail for these "low

bandwidth" applications. These cost reductions may occur due to innovative manufacturing and integration technology or by permitting modification of the FDDI "standard" to permit use of alternative low cost fiber optic components for the physical layer of the network. Since the standard has been altered to permit copper rather than fiber, perhaps the standard for the physical layer of FDDI should also be modified to permit the use of a new generation of low cost components and to rekindle the market for the optical version of the network. Since local area networks are designed as self contained communications systems, flexibility in the physical layer can be easily accommodated with the component appropriate specifications just as is being done with the TSP and UTP versions.

In addition to the local area network standard, the commercial computer industry is also defining high bandwidth serial data transmission standards to interconnect computer peripherals to processors. Fibre Channel which operates at 1.06 Gbits per second and serial HIPPI (high performance parallel interface) which operates at 1.2 Gbits per second are two such standards which define the data protocol and transmission rates for point-to-point links and are gaining wide industry acceptance. The computer interface hardware is being developed in integrated circuit format and the electro-optic interfaces have been defined. Most serial standards are scalable from several hundred megabits per second to gigabits per second. The high bandwidth of these channels combined with bandwidth compression techniques allows for the transmission of multimedia information over a serial channel.

ARPA, with matching industry funding, is currently sponsoring an industry consortia to investigate high speed optical interconnect technology for advanced computers. The effort is emphasizing high bandwidth (500Mhz) parallel channels with arrays of lasers and receivers interconnected over a ribbon fiber optic cable. Hardware from these developments will provide architecture alternatives to serial transmission for advanced computer interconnects.

High bandwidth architectures (i.e. backplanes) are also being investigated for the internal communications channels in advanced computers. These are required for multiprocessor distributed processing requiring cache memory coherence. The Scaleable Coherent Interface (SCI) defined by the IEEE 1596 committee is such an architecture comprised of high speed links which can be reconfigured to form ringlets or cross bar switched configurations. Gigabit per second data rates are being proposed for these applications with both copper and fiber as the transmission media.

B: THE COMMUNICATIONS INDUSTRY

While the computer industry debates the issues involved in networks and high bandwidth peripheral links, the communications industry is pushing the limits on bandwidth for their industry telecommunication link standards. The SONET (synchronous optical network) standards define the physical transport layer for a family of point-to-point fiber optic links which operate at frequencies compatible with the existing copper telecommunications standards and extend the

transmission rates into the gigahertz band by continually doubling the rate. Both the data protocol and electro-optic hardware are defined for these links. The highest data rate currently emerging is the OC48 rate which operates at 2.488 Gbits per second and efforts are underway to extend this data interface standard to nearly 10 Ghz.

ATM (Asynchronous Transfer Mode) is a communications protocol standard residing just above the physical layer and defines the user to network interface or the network to network interface. ATM is defined independent of the physical layer and the input data stream is asynchronous with respect to the physical transport of the cells. Cells are created and then synchronized to the physical layer of the network, such as SONET. The physical layer can be SONET, Fibre Channel or any other suitable standard. A 48 octet data payload was chosen for the ATM standard with a five octet header. Path and channel identifiers are provided for switching paths or channels. Paths within a network are selected to guarantee the same order of delivery as the order of transmission. While a quality of service is guaranteed there is no absolute guarantee of delivery and the upper layers must handle cell loss. Connections can be point-to-point or multicast. An industry forum has been formed for implementation of this standard. Although many of the protocol choices are not optimum for computer applications, the computer industry is considering using this standard as a possible LAN interface to assure compatibility with communications protocols

C: CABLE TELEVISION INDUSTRY

The cable television industry is also progressing in development of broadband technology for fiber-to-the-home applications. The emphasis to date has been on analog rather than the all digital transmission being pursued by the phone companies in order to be compatible with the existing cable coaxial transmission. Vestigial sideband analog transmission has been the preferred method of transmission since it is the format used by terrestrial broadcasters and CATV operators

The use of sub-carrier based fiber optic transmission offers a very attractive method of combining analog and digital information on the same network as the previously mentioned TIES system demonstrated over coaxial cable. A sub-carrier modulation transmitter contains a large number of rf or microwave oscillators that serve as carriers for either digital or analog baseband signals. The modulated electrical carriers are power combined, amplified and used to modulate a wideband laser or external modulator. After transmission over an optical fiber, a PIN or avalanche photodetector and front-end electronic amplifier are used to select and recover the transmitted electrical sub-carriers. Because of the enormous bandwidth of SCM transmission, the use of current analog or digital standards over separate sub-carriers can be retained and new standards can be implemented over the network as needed with the addition of additional interface electronics.

Wavelength division multiplexing also provides an alternative optical carrier based system to add bandwidth as needed to a network. Unfortunately the temperature instability of the

currently available optical sources presents problems for aircraft applications limiting the number of usable wavelengths. Technological improvements are needed to capitalize on the possibilities of WDM technology over aircraft temperature extremes.

BROADBAND NETWORKS ON AIRCRAFT

Even though baseband networks are just being introduced on both military and commercial aircraft, the need for increased bandwidth and the emergence of a new family of photonic devices is stimulating the interest in broadband networks. The use of the above mentioned base band or carrier based broadband technologies are being explored for passenger entertainment systems on commercial aircraft. Systems of this type will provide multiple channels of on-board video, real time television and two-way digital communications for passenger shopping, telephone or telefax services. The military is interested in broadband networks to transfer broadband sensor and video data onboard the aircraft and to interconnect with external networks as part of a global grid.

The emphasis on dual use technology development and the incorporation of commercial standards into military systems provides a unique opportunity for both the industry and the military. The use of commercial standards can dramatically reduce the front-end cost in developing advanced avionics architectures. The defense emphasis on developing rugged components can provide extremely reliable components for commercial applications such as automobiles and industrial controls. The volume required to reduce cost can be provided by the commercial marketplace with joint front-end component development to provide reliability and quality through improved manufacturing technology.

A NEW GENERATION OF FIBER OPTIC COMPONENT TECHNOLOGY

The current family of hardware planned for aircraft networks consists of multimode components and moderate data rate transmission. The optical sources are LEDs operating in the 850-1300 nanometer spectrum. The connectors are variants of the existing electrical connectors with optical termini inserts. Hybrid star couplers and electro-mechanical switches are used in network distribution. This first generation of specially designed hardware is expected to perform well in aerospace platforms but the costs will remain high due to the relatively low volume and labor intensive manufacturing and assembly costs. As confidence builds with experience in the technology with this first generation hardware, we can look forward to the next generation which is now emerging from the telecommunications and computer laboratories.

Laser technology has progressed to the point where it is now possible to achieve operation over the full military range with "conventional" or modified heterostructure devices. These high temperature devices are not commercial off-the-shelf products but are specially developed and packaged devices. In addition to these first generation lasers, we are now seeing the development of novel quantum well structures and miniature "glass" lasers with enormous potential for both the commercial and military

markets. These include vertical cavity surface emitting lasers (VCSELs) and miniature diode pumped glass lasers. Because of the low threshold currents, high efficiency and high frequency operation, VCSELs open new possibilities for computer interconnects and broadband networks. The VCSEL technology can dramatically reduce the cost of lasers since arrays of devices can be batch fabricated on large semiconductor wafers. The wavelength of these devices can also be varied across a wafer with very regular spacing to provide interesting possibilities for wavelength division multiplexing. Miniature YAG slab or cube lasers which are diode pumped also present a next generation alternative for avionics because of their high output power and potential for operation in severe environments. Because of the continuous nature of the output signal for optimum operation, these lasers will require an external semiconductor or integrated optic modulator.

In most aerospace applications the optical power budget has been a major concern when implementing fiber optic networks. The telecommunications industry and electro-optic component suppliers are investing heavily in optical amplifiers which provide signal gain for signals travelling down optical fibers. This eliminates the need for repeaters which must be designed for a specific data format. The use of optical amplification using both erbium doped fiber amplifiers as well as semiconductor amplifiers allows the network to be upgraded to higher data rates or different protocols without replacing the entire physical layer of the network. These gain elements can also be very useful in network architectures which must service a large number of users such as aircraft passenger entertainment systems.

Notable advances have been made in integrating arrays of PIN diodes and entire receivers which can interface with the laser diode arrays. These devices can be aligned to fiber arrays using "silicon bench" methods which will permit cost effective redundancy switching concepts and fault tolerant network management.

A new generation of cables and connectors is also emerging which is based on photolithographically defined and chemically etched silicon or ceramic substrates to provide precise alignment. The use of these concepts and microlens advances present enormous potential for packaging the laser arrays and providing an expanded beam lens connector family which provides fiber facet protection and ease of alignment. Ribbon fiber cables are also emerging to provide an extremely redundant cabling system which can be batch terminated with the above mentioned array connectors. These array connectors can also provide the precise alignment need to permit the entry of single mode fibers into military systems.

The ability to produce militarized couplers for fiber optics networks presented problems during early aircraft network development programs and are still a high cost item in aircraft networks. New coupler technology which uses pyrolytically deposited silica waveguides on silicon substrates are now commercially available to produce a "coupler on a chip" This chip can be integrated into a fiber optic transmitter package or

even into a connector and can survive the military environment since the technology is the same as that now used in integrated circuits.

Optical switches can be obtained from commercial foundries and can be very useful in redundancy management and fault tolerant architectures. These components are single mode integrated optic waveguide devices and must be optimized for military environments.

REQUIRED DEVELOPMENTS FOR SECOND GENERATION AIRCRAFT NETWORKS

A full family of second generation fiber optic hardware must now be developed if we are to capitalize on the new industry thrusts in high performance networks. This second generation hardware should include a ribbon cable plant consisting of ruggedized cables including both single mode and multimode fibers, high density array connectors, and chip couplers. The active components including lasers, amplifiers, detector arrays and switches must be optimized, ruggedized and packaged for the aerospace environment.

Network architectures must be optimized with respect to fault tolerance to meet the high reliability requirements of our aircraft. Commercial protocols should be used when applicable with implementation with militarized hardware. Broadband networks can provide extremely high payoff add should receive further emphasis. The telecommunications and cable television industry developments to date provide a good technology base which can be optimized for specific aerospace requirements. These advance networks can provide the capacity to store all aircraft maintenance manuals and permit a history of aircraft maintenance to be stored onboard. This can greatly improve our maintenance and logistics system to minimize downtime and facilitate repairs.

All new baseband and broadband networks should provide built-in-test and real time reconfiguration capability in the network itself to eliminate the need for special test and maintenance equipment. The use of redundant ribbon cables and modular packaging should permit introduction of this capability without cost and weight penalty.

Another opportunity to capitalize on commercial developments is in the area of optical computer backplanes. The use of these serialized backplanes which can be reconfigured with switched or ring architectures will be compatible with the new proposed industry standards. The Navy optical backplane interconnect system (OBIS) and Air Force very high speed optical network (VHSON) programs will be demonstrating these advanced concepts over the next two years. These backplanes will facilitate distributed and massively parallel processing using the ever advancing commercial microprocessor technology. The technology should also be compatible with the new industry backplane standards such as SCI.

FLY-BY-LIGHT SYSTEMS

The criticality of ultra-reliable hardware and fault tolerant architectures is driven by aircraft control system applications.

"Fly-By-Light" technology uses all optical sensors and actuators to control both the airframe surfaces and the engine parameters. Signals from the feedback sensors can be transferred over fiber optic networks to the redundant flight control computers. A combination of sensing techniques can be employed including analog and digital code plates, interferometers, phosphorescent decay, black body radiation et al. These sensor signals can be decoded by standard electro-optic interface modules which can interrogate many sensors and multiplex the digitized data onto the network.

The fiber optic control system integration (FOCSI) program will be flight testing fiber optic sensors for both the flight and engine control systems of an F-18 aircraft in the fall of 1993 at the NASA Dryden test facility. This joint NASA/Navy development will obtain essential in-flight performance and reliability data on the sensor complement while providing information on installation, maintenance and operational problems on advanced aircraft.

REQUIRED FLY-BY-LIGHT DEVELOPMENT

After completion of the FOCSI program, a near term follow-on closed loop flight test will be required to demonstrate fly-by-light aircraft control system performance. The development and demonstration of optically controlled actuators will need to be incorporated into this demonstration to provide a total optical capability. A fault tolerant architecture which includes network and distributed computing redundancy must also be included. Optical backplane technology can enhance the reliability of fly-by-light systems and should be incorporated when available.

Fiber optic sensors must be continually be improved and optimized for aerospace applications. Additional emphasis on standardization and modularity must be achieved through both network and sensor interface standards. The medium range objectives for fly-by-light systems should include a totally integrated flight/propulsion system with off-engine controls and a long term goal of fly-by-light systems should include the first introduction of analog optical computing. The industrial technology base must continue to support novel sensor concepts and innovative manufacturing technology to improve quality and reduce costs.

SMART SKINS AND STRUCTURES

Smart skins and structures technology involves the use of sensors and communications links embedded in composite structures. Although the sensors and links can be electrical or optical in nature, I will briefly discuss the optical implementation of this technology.

By observing the parameters of light which passes through optical fibers placed in the composite structure including intensity polarization and wavelength in response to different physical phenomena, one can correlate the output and effect to produce a self contained sensor. The optimum "smart structure" sensor responds to only one physical parameter and does not affect the desired materials property of the structure. Interferometers, and intensity sensors are the most common.

Simple fatigue cracking in composites can be detected through the use of optical time domain reflectometry. Addition research is continuing on optimum sensor configuration to optimize structural properties, as well as connector and coupler schemes and signal processing to optimize sensor performance.

Optical fibers and optical fiber sensors provide a compatible media for transmitting and sensing information in the structure of an aerospace vehicle. The extensive use of composite materials to provide lighter and stronger materials with reduced radar cross section has presented challenges to materials and structures engineers. It is highly desirable to place sensors in a structure to constantly monitor strain or to detect potential or actual defects in the material while in flight. Sensors can also be used to monitor the high temperatures and pressures occurring within the material layers as the structure is fabricated in the autoclave. The embedding of fiber optic data transmission and structural monitoring sensors with the structure is commonly known as "smart structure" technology. The use of embedded piezoelectrics or other memory metals to provide structural motion control of structural surfaces is also commonly included in this definition.

Common composite materials range from the fiberglass epoxy used in automobiles and boats to graphite epoxy or silicon carbide epoxy combinations used in modern aircraft. Exotic fiber filaments can also be added to metals to enhance their strength and high temperature properties. The most common fabrication techniques involve the use of woven cloth of the structural fibers which are pre-pregnated with an epoxy or adhesive coating. These fabrics are alternately layered with the epoxy resins to build up a desired thickness of material which is then placed in an autoclave and "cured" under controlled heat and pressure to form the final structure.

Smart skin technology involves embedding both microwave and optical sensors in the skin of the aircraft. The "eyes and ears" of the aircraft become a part of the aircraft skin. Embedded phased array antennas and distributed optical sensors are key elements of the technology. Major efforts are underway to investigate the use of optical fibers embedded in the skin to send array control signals to the radar elements and to send the receive signals to remotely located signal processors. The signals from the optical sensors likewise can be transmitted directly to signal processors or digitized prior to transmission depending on the optical spectrum and the length of signal transmission. The same embedment issues which affect the structural and material properties of composites by embedding these transmission paths must be addressed. A recent process for weaving optical fibers into structural fiber fabric should lead to a simplification of the embedment process and ease the connectorization problem due to the regular spacing of the fibers.

CONCLUSIONS

The first generation of fiber optic networks and hardware is finally heading for production in both military and commercial aircraft. We cannot declare a victory and move on to other technologies. A wealth of technology is following in rapid

succession which will provide vastly improved capability over and above that of first generation technology. This second generation technology will also require ruggedization and packaging before it can transition into aerospace applications. This will not occur without strong financial support from both industry and government. The emphasis on commonality and dual use photonic technology can serve to reduce development and production costs for both military and commercial applications and enhance our domestic competitiveness. I believe that photonic technology has finally arrived for aircraft applications and I hope we can look ahead to the year 2000 when photonic technology becomes the technology of choice for both information transmission and control systems in aerospace applications.